

Report on The Impact of On-line Filtering on The Discovery Potential

Vladimir Lenok¹ and Dominik Schwarz¹

¹Universität Bielefeld

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Abstract

The report provides a brief summary of the findings of work on data irreversibility related to the impact of the on-line filtering of data on the potential to discover yet unknown and perhaps even unexpected signals. For the time being we focus on radio astronomical data streams to develop approaches and methods to evaluate the impact of on-line filtering on the discovery potential. We found an unified approach to describe the filtering of different kinds and identified preliminary approaches to measure the amount of information in data streams in the framework of the Shannon information theory. We present a possible way to generalize the signal detection procedure in the context of the statistical signal detection and show a particular example how this generalization influences the signal discovery potential.

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1 Problems and scope of the work

Plenty of research fields in contemporary science face similar or even the same challenges related to large data volumes, large data rates, diversity of the informative and nuisance signals, and all of that leads to the need of applying one or the other kind of on-line filtering. Even though solutions of such problems differs depending on the application, there are general tendencies to utilize ideas from the hypothesis testing and information theory to address the emerging problems [1–6]. Despite using such a common ideas and approaches, it appears that currently these challenges appearing in various fields are not treated within a common framework. The first aim of this project is to establish such a framework that will allow one to harmonize approaches and solutions used in different fields and provide a coherent picture of the information flows in systems and pipelines disregard particular application or instrumentation. To approach a possible solution for that complex problem, we use astronomical radio telescope data streams as the example for our current work.

The data streams that are under consideration in this work are discrete-time data. Namely, the incoming continuous data are discretized both in time and amplitude. Within the scope of our work, we focus our attention to the data that are discretized only over time: discrete-time time series.

Here we address the following main problems:

1. Identification of an example problem and its data types for further development of methods and techniques.
2. Identification and clarification of terminology.
3. Finding approaches towards a unified view of the problem of filtering.
4. Finding approaches to estimate of amount of information coming to the filtration system.
5. Finding approaches to estimate the discovery potential of a given data stream.
6. Identifying approaches to evaluate the impact of the filtration procedures to the discovery potential.

2 Terms and definitions

2.1 Data

1. **Data** — an additive combination of signal and noise. The type, nature, and features of the signal and noise can differ from application to application.

2.2 Signal

In the context of information theory, a “signal” is described as “a form of representation of information for transmission via a channel, which is an aggregate of means for information transmission, including a physical medium.” [7] The means of information transmission in radio astronomy are electromagnetic waves and electric currents and voltages. Thus, within the scope of this report, we narrow down the meaning of the term “signal” to the electrical signals emerging in the output of the receiving system of a radio telescope (in the jargon of radio astronomy: the backend of the receiving system).

1. **Signal** — single or group of time series representing a discrete-time sample of the electromagnetic field observed by an instrument and carrying the meaningful information about the object or phenomena under observation. The time series under consideration are voltage or current as functions of time (synonym: **waveform**). In general, these functions can be continuous or have other forms (see two following terms).
2. **Discrete-time signal** — a signal defined only on discrete time domain.
3. **Digital signal** — a discrete-time signal whose amplitude is defined on discrete domain.

4. **Energy of signal** — if signal $s(t)$ is either voltage or current, $s^2(t)$ is the instant power dissipated on 1Ω resistance and the integral of this quantity over time is the energy E of the signal [8]

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s^2(t) dt = E. \quad (1)$$

2.3 Noise

1. **Noise** — type of signals that do not carry meaningful information about the object or phenomena under observation (synonyms: **nuisance signals**, **radio-frequency interference signals**).

2.4 Filtration

1. **Filtering** — analysis procedures aiming to perform at least one of the following actions: detect signal, reduce noise, enhance signal-to-noise ratio, reduce amount of data, or/and compress data (synonyms: **data reduction**)
2. **On-line filtering** — a filtering that is fast enough to be applied to the data stream coming from an instrument.
3. **Off-line filtering** — a filtering that is either not fast enough to be applied during receiving the data or that is intended to be used with the data on-line filtered before.
4. **Linear time-invariant filter** — a filter performing time-invariant linear transformation of incoming signals. The signal $s'(t)$ on the output of such a filter in the time domain is defined as a convolution of the incoming signal $s(t)$ with the impulse response of the filter $u(t)$

$$s'(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} s(\tau)u(t - \tau) d\tau. \quad (2)$$

The corresponding output in the Fourier domain is

$$\mathbf{S}'(\omega) = \mathbf{S}(\omega)\mathbf{U}(\omega), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{S}(\omega)$ and $\mathbf{S}'(\omega)$ denote the complex Fourier image of the input and output signals correspondingly, and $\mathbf{U}(\omega)$ is the complex Fourier image of the filter response.

5. **Impulse response** — the response of the filter for the delta-functional input signal

$$u(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(\tau)u(t - \tau) d\tau. \quad (4)$$

6. **Optimal filter** — the filter which provides the maximum signal-to-noise ratio for a given signal (see the corresponding section of the report).
7. **Discovery potential** — a measure estimating the probability to detect an arbitrary signal in observed data.

In the case of the discrete-time signals (with the discretization time Δt), all above mentioned integrals get converted to the corresponding sums such as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t) dt \leftrightarrow \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} f_i \Delta t. \quad (5)$$

2.5 Comments about particular terms

Signal and Noise. Both the signal and noise are time series representing the observed data.

Discovery potential. For the current stage of the development the definition 7 should be slightly refined. Namely, the term “discovery potential” we understand as a probability to detect a signal of certain class in discrete-time series containing in addition a sample of a stationary stochastic process representing the “noise” that is unavoidable in any measurements. Since, in the context of radio astronomy the signal undergo dispersion during the propagation from its source to the observer, at the current stage of research and development we assume that the interesting signals should be from the class of the dispersed signals.

3 Typical science questions addressed with individual radio antennas

A single telescope or a single antenna of a large-scale radio interferometer is traditionally used for radio-astronomical observations of distant objects and phenomena in the Universe that do not require high angular resolution. The single telescope observations are limited in angle by the beam main-lobe width and provide important temporal observations of transients. Thus, it is worth identifying the range of tasks that may arise on the level of an individual antenna:

1. detection of pulsar signals and measuring their parameters (including discovery and regular measurements),
2. detection of fast-radio-burst signals and measuring their parameters,
3. detection of various dispersed signals that can be associated with quasars or other astrophysical sources,
4. spectral measurements of particular sources.

Of course, the tasks that can be solved with individual radio telescopes are not limited to the short list shown above. However, it is apparent that a large group of them is connected to some extent to the signal detection and the measurement of the parameters of such detected signals. The theory of statistical signal detection allows for having a view to a large number of problems from general perspectives. Since the target of the current work is the discovery potential, we will focus on the statistical signal detection and will put aside the questions connected to the estimation of the parameters of signals.

4 General statistical view of signal detection

Statistical signal detection is a logical extension of the ideas developed in the framework of hypothesis testing to the realm of signal processing or generally speaking to the realms of time series analysis. The framework of hypothesis testing which we consider is based on the Bayesian approach to signal detection. This approach will help us to identify a deep logical connection between diverse methods for signal identification.

4.1 Gaussian white noise process as a noise model

In the work we limit ourselves to the case of white noise, which is a good approximation for a large variety of noises that appear in practice for band-limited signals, and, at the same time, has good mathematical properties that allow us to obtain important analytical results. The following list summarizes the assumptions that were made about the noise:

1. The noise is additive, stationary, and belongs to the class of quasi-white noise with a flat spectrum in the frequency band from 0 to f_{\max} .
2. The instant values of the noise are distributed according to the normal distribution with zero expected value.

According to these assumptions the probability density distribution of the noise signal values are

$$p(y_k) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi n_0}} e^{-\frac{y_k^2}{2n_0}}, \quad (6)$$

where n_0^2 is the variance of the noise.

The analysis of autocorrelation functions provide clear connection of the power spectral density of the noise $N_0/2$ (value of $\mathbf{S}^2(\omega)$ in the band from $-f_{\max}$ to f_{\max}) and the variance of the band-limited quasi-white noise n_0^2 . Namely

$$n_0^2 = N_0 f_{\max}. \quad (7)$$

4.2 Bayesian signal detection

The Bayesian approach to signal detection in the variant we are dealing with in the present work considers the following framework [1–5, 9, 10]. There are two possible physical situations: the signal is present in the time series (A_1) or the time series does not contain the signal (A_0). Then, there is a decision making (or measurement) procedure. It can make only one of the two possible decisions: the procedure decides that there is the signal in the data (A_1^*), or that there is no signal (A_0^*). The index denotes the signal type, the asterisk denotes the decision type. Thus, there exist four possible situations in this framework written symbolically (the corresponding conditional probabilities with their short notations are introduced in the brackets):

- $A_0^*A_0$ — correct non-detection ($\hat{F} = P(A_0^*|A_0)$),
- $A_1^*A_0$ — “false alarm” or “false positive” detection ($F = P(A_1^*|A_0)$),
- $A_0^*A_1$ — missing the signal ($\hat{D} = P(A_0^*|A_1)$),

- $A_1^*A_1$ — correct detection of the signal ($D = P(A_1^*|A_1)$).

The current framework does not consider repetitive estimations. Thus, the decision must be made after one observation.

The following basic property holds within the present framework

$$P(A_0^*, A_0) + P(A_1^*, A_0) + P(A_0^*, A_1) + P(A_1^*, A_1) = 1. \quad (8)$$

This property is the basis for the Bayesian signal detection approach.

A central quantity in this approach is the mean risk to err, \bar{r} . It is build upon the basic property above by adding a factor in front of each joint probability function

$$\bar{r} = \sum_i r_i P_i = r_1 P(A_0^*, A_0) + r_2 P(A_1^*, A_0) + r_3 P(A_0^*, A_1) + r_4 P(A_1^*, A_1). \quad (9)$$

Each of the factors r_i denotes the risk associated with a particular decision given the presence or absence of the signal in the data. Since the situation of correct identification of presence or absence of the signal does not lead to any risk, the corresponding factors are put to zeros ($r_1 = 0$ and $r_4 = 0$). The remaining risk factors we rename according to the associated situations ($r_F = r(A_1^*, A_0)$ for “false alarm” and $r_{\hat{D}} = r(A_0^*, A_1)$ for missing signal)

$$\bar{r} = r_F P(A_1^*, A_0) + r_{\hat{D}} P(A_0^*, A_1). \quad (10)$$

As a next step, we use the following standard equations from probability theory to convert joint probabilities into conditional probabilities

$$P(A_1^*, A_0) = P(A_0)P(A_1^*|A_0) = P(A_0)F, \quad (11)$$

$$P(A_0^*, A_1) = P(A_1)P(A_0^*|A_1) = P(A_1)\hat{D}. \quad (12)$$

Thus, the distributions $P(A_0)$ and $P(A_1)$ summarize our *a priori* knowledge about the noise and the signal. After this conversion, we come to the main equation for the mean risk in the Bayesian signal detection approach

$$\bar{r} = r_F F P(A_0) + r_{\hat{D}} \hat{D} P(A_1). \quad (13)$$

This equation is the basis for the rich variety of detection criteria and methods that we will see in the next section.

4.3 Various detection criteria

Before discussing criteria appearing from the mean risk, we should introduce another important criterion in the context of Bayesian hypothesis testing. Quite often the situation during the observations is such that we have knowledge about the noise and at the same time we want to suppress or to some extent control the rate of the “false alarms” appearing in the system. The Newman–Pearson criterion targets such a situation. According to this criterion, the “false alarm” rate may be fixed to a desired level and then the rate of correct identification of the signal is maximized in the corresponding parameter space. For example, this maximization can be done in the space of individual thresholds for the time trace. This criterion has a general nature and can be used in various situations. Especially, in those where there is no information about the expected signals.

The mean risk (13) gives the foundation for different detection criteria. Firstly, let us note that the risks for the two situations (false alarm and missed detection) in the formula for the mean risk have different values in general. However, we could decide to make them equal and – in this case – without losing generality put them equal to unity (which would correspond to putting them in front of the entire equation and then noticing that such a constant scaling factor does not affect the overall shape of the function). This consideration leads to the following equation

$$\bar{r} = FP(A_0) + \hat{D}P(A_1). \quad (14)$$

Procedures build on minimization this risk are called the criteria of ideal observer.

Secondly, to obtain other criteria, let us rewrite the general expression (13) for the mean risk in the following way

$$\bar{r} = r_{\hat{D}}P(A_1) - [D - l_0F] r_{\hat{D}}P(A_1), \quad (15)$$

where we used $D + \hat{D} = 1$ and defined the factor l_0 as the ratio of the *a priori* distributions and the risk factors,

$$l_0 = \frac{r_F P(A_0)}{r_{\hat{D}} P(A_1)}. \quad (16)$$

Analysis of the equation (15) for the mean risk shows that the combination $r_{\hat{D}}P(A_1)$ always remains the same and depends only on the *a priori* knowledge about the probability $P(A_1)$ to observe the signal and the desired value of the risk to miss it, $r_{\hat{D}}$. Thus, to minimize the mean risk, it is sufficient to maximize the equation in the brackets. Writing this statement formally gives the following so-called weighting criterion

$$\operatorname{argmax}_{D,F} (D - l_0F), \quad (17)$$

which shows that l_0 has the meaning of a weighting factor with which we take into account the influence of the “false alarm” rate.

To move forward, let us consider a model that is a good initial approximation for the signal processing in the context of radio astronomy. Namely, the model of a known signal in non-coherent, Gaussian, white noise. First, we consider a one dimensional variant of this model. Let the measured signal y be the additive combination of the signal of a fixed constant value x and a fluctuating white noise with zero mean and known variance

$$y = x + n. \quad (18)$$

For this case of a fixed-value signal we can write the conditional probabilities of expected signals

$$p(y|A_0) = p_n(y), \quad (19)$$

$$p(y|A_1) = p_{sn}(y). \quad (20)$$

If we introduce the decision rule $A^*(y)$ selecting the region of the measured signal values y that correspond to the presence of signal, we can write the explicit expressions for the probability D to detect the signal in case of the actual presence of the signal and the probability F to detect the signal in case of the absence of signal

$$D = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A^*(y) p_{sn}(y) dy, \quad (21)$$

$$F = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A^*(y) p_n(y) dy. \quad (22)$$

When we use these equations in the formula (17) for the weighting criterion, we come to the following integral expression for it

$$D - l_0 F = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} A^*(y) p_n(y) [l(y) - l_0] dy. \quad (23)$$

The term $l(y)$ appearing in the equation is the likelihood ratio

$$l(y) = \frac{p_{sn}(y)}{p_n(y)}. \quad (24)$$

The analysis of equation (23) shows that the weighting criterion can be reduced to maximization of likelihood ratio which makes a new criterion logically connected to the Bayesian approach to the signal detection.

Up to this point we did not use any assumptions regarding the Gaussian character of the distributions. If we make such an assumption, we arrive at a particular equation for the likelihood ratio

$$l(y) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{(y-x)^2}{2n_0^2}\right)}{\exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2n_0^2}\right)} = \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2n_0^2}\right) \exp\left(\frac{xy}{n_0^2}\right). \quad (25)$$

To see the situation more clearly let us extend this one-dimensional example to larger number of dimensions. Namely, let us assume now that the signal that we expect has not only one value, but has multiple values. This situation naturally corresponds to the observation of discrete-time signals in radio astronomy. For such a multidimensional situation, the equation (25) has the straightforward generalization

$$l(y) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2n_0^2} \sum_i x_i^2 \Delta t\right) \exp\left(\frac{1}{n_0^2} \sum_i x_i y_i \Delta t\right). \quad (26)$$

If we extend the example to the case of continuous signals, we formally substitute sums with the corresponding integrals

$$l(y) = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2n_0^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2 dt\right) \exp\left(\frac{1}{n_0^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} xy dt\right). \quad (27)$$

Now we clearly see the correlation sums and integrals in arguments of the exponents. The meaning of them remain the same as previously: squared sum or integral of the expected signal is its energy, the other sum or integral provides a measure of correlation between the expected signal and the observed data.

If we analyze equations (26) and (27), we can see that the first exponential term is a constant with a fixed value as soon as the expected signal is known. The functional dependence is hold by the second term. We can rewrite the same equations neglecting non-essential constants that do not hold any information regarding the functional behaviour of the likelihood ratio. For the discrete case we have

$$\ln l(y) = \sum_i x_i y_i \Delta t, \quad (28)$$

and for the continuous one

$$\ln l(y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} xy \, dt. \quad (29)$$

In this form it becomes apparent that maximization of the likelihood ratio is equivalent to the maximization of the correlation between the signal and data and, thus, can be reduced to it.

Up to this point we have identified a logical connection between the Bayes approach to signal detection, the maximization of likelihood ratio, the maximization of correlation, and few other methods that appeared in natural connection to the Bayes risk and its analysis. To take one more step forward let us consider the optimal filter and some of its fundamental properties. As it will be visible that this kind of filter is logically connected to the correlation that appeared in the formulas above.

4.4 Optimal filter

The filter is called optimal when it maximizes the output signal-to-noise ratio [8, 10].

Probably, the fastest way to obtain the properties of the filter which is optimal for the white noise is to consider the absolute value of signal-to-noise ratio at the output of a linear filter in frequency domain [8]

$$\frac{|s_{out}|}{\sigma_{out}} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{out}} \left| \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(\omega) e^{i\theta_s(\omega)} U(\omega) e^{i\phi_u(\omega)+i\omega t_0} \, d\omega \right|. \quad (30)$$

Here σ denotes the standard deviation of the noise at the output. The product $S(\omega)e^{i\theta_s(\omega)}$ is the Fourier image of the incoming signal. The product $U(\omega)e^{i\phi_u(\omega)+i\omega t_0}$ is the characteristics of the linear filter with t_0 denoting the delay of the filter before the maximum signal-to-noise ratio point in time, and $U(\omega)$ and $\phi_u(\omega)$ being the amplitude and phase response of the filter.

To find the conditions of the optimal filter, we should find what is the maximum absolute value the signal-to-noise ratio can attain. To do so, let us consider the maximum that the absolute value of integral in (30) can attain.

The Cauchy–Schwarz inequality reads

$$\left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F_1(x) F_2(x) \, dx \right|^2 \leq \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |F_1(x)|^2 \, dx \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |F_2(x)|^2 \, dx. \quad (31)$$

Let $F_1(\omega) = S(\omega)e^{i\theta_s(\omega)}$, $F_2(\omega) = U(\omega)e^{i\phi_u(\omega)+i\omega t_0}$. Using this inequality and the regular equation for the noise at the output of the filter we obtain the following equation for the signal-to-noise ratio

$$\frac{|s_{out}|}{\sigma_{out}} \leq \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S^2(\omega) \, d\omega \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(\omega) \, d\omega}}{\sqrt{\frac{N_0}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K^2(\omega) \, d\omega}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_0}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S^2(\omega) \, d\omega}. \quad (32)$$

The later radical is equal to the energy of the expected signal (let letter E denotes it). Thus, we can write

$$\frac{|s_{out}|}{\sigma_{out}} \leq \sqrt{\frac{E}{N_0}}. \quad (33)$$

The right hand side of the inequality is the maximum attainable value of the signal-to-noise ratio for a linear filter. For the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, we know when it becomes an equality, which means that the filter becomes optimal. Here are the conditions for that

$$K(\omega) = AS(\omega), \quad A \in \mathbb{R} \quad (34)$$

$$\phi_u(\omega) + \omega t_0 + 2\pi n = -\theta_s(\omega), \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (35)$$

Here, the letter A denotes an arbitrary constant. These conditions show that in order to make the filter optimal one should match the characteristics of the expected signal which gives another name for this filter — the matched filter.

Impulse response of the optimal filter g matches to the shape of the expected signal $s(t)$ in the time domain

$$g(t) = As(t_0 - t). \quad (36)$$

The time delay t_0 is a fixed parameter that is required to make the filter causal. Also, this is the point in time when the maximum signal appears at the filter output. Its presence can be also rigorously obtained from analytical computations [8]. Using this impulse response we can write the equation for the output signal of the optimal filter in the time domain.

$$z(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y(\tau)g(t - \tau) d\tau = A \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y(\tau)s(t_0 - t + \tau) d\tau, \quad (37)$$

which at t_0 becomes

$$z(t_0) = A \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} y(\tau)s(\tau) d\tau. \quad (38)$$

This formula reveals that the maximum signal at the output of the optimal filter is equal to the correlation integral of the expected signal and the data that appeared in the analysis of the likelihood ratio for the Gaussian noise (29).

The connection that we showed between the Bayes signal detection and the theory of optimal filtration gives a different perspective to the correlation measurement that naturally appeared in our consideration of the maximum likelihood ratio for the Gaussian noise. The list below summarizes the properties observed in this connection:

- The correlation that appeared in the maximum likelihood ratio (26) can be thought of as the peak output signal of the optimal or matched filter (36).
- The highest possible signal-to-noise ratio that correlation-type measurements can attain occurs while correlating the signal with itself.
- The result of the correlation measurement depends only on the energy of the signal and does not depend on the shape of the signal or any other parameters of the signal.

- In the framework of linear filters, the highest possible signal-to-noise ratio in any correlation-type measurement is obtained when correlating the signal with itself. Any other signal decomposition schemes (that are also correlations of a given time trace with a test signal of desired type) will lead to lower signal-to-noise ratio.
- The deeper analysis of the optimal filter shows that the filter can be split into few stages (phase part only and spectral type only), and that it can be constructed in a way the optimal filtration includes frequency shifts and other signal processing techniques (for details see [3]).
- If we look at the optimal filter (and at the linear filter in general) from the perspective of Bayes signal detection, we can see that this kind of filters can be treated statistically. This means that by applying methods of statistical hypothesis testing considered above, the noise-only signal components can be identified and rejected, corresponding to some level of confidence, from the analysis or data compression procedure.

For further development of the connection between the Bayes signal detection and linear filtration, we should identify relevant statistical properties of the correlation sums or integrals.

4.5 Statistical properties of the correlation sums and integrals

It was shown above that the correlation-type measurement play the central role in the optimal and linear filtration and Bayes signal detection. To use correlation or filtration procedures appearing in different contexts as a part of statistical signal processing procedures, we should clarify the statistical properties of the correlation sums and integrals. Hereafter in this section we consider the correlation integrals. The results for the sums are identical.

Here is the correlation integral that appears in different contexts

$$z = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t)y(t) dt.$$

Function $x(t)$ denotes the shape of expected signal in the time domain. Function $y(t)$ denotes the observed data. To study statistical properties of this correlation integral, let us consider the data consisting of the expected signal and the Gaussian white noise $n(t)$ with zero mean and known variance n_0^2

$$y(t) = x(t) + n(t). \quad (39)$$

While $x(t)$ is a regular function here, $n(t)$ is a particular realisation of the Gaussian white noise process, that makes it a random function (for details see [10]).

The statistical properties of this integral are known in the general literature on statistics [10]. Since the $y(t)$ is the Gaussian process, the $z(t)$ is the Gaussian process too with the mean and variance given by the following expressions

$$\mathbb{E}[z] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2(t) dt = E, \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbb{V}[z] = n_0^2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2(t) dt = n_0^2 E. \quad (41)$$

Where as before E denotes the energy of the expected signal.

If the observed process consists of the noise only ($y(t) = n(t)$), the mean and the variance get the form

$$\mathbb{E}[z] = 0, \quad (42)$$

$$\mathbb{V}[z] = n_0^2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x^2(t) dt = n_0^2 E. \quad (43)$$

Even though these results are known, in the context of the statistical view at the correlations they highlight important fundamental properties and corresponding limitations of the correlation integrals for the signals with noise. The obtained property shows that the Gaussian character of the origin noise propagates to the correlation coefficients, and the variance of the noise propagates to the variance of the correlation coefficients linearly with energy. This fundamental property of the correlation integrals and sums imply limitations on values of the coefficients that can be associated with noise only. Moreover, since the Gaussian property propagates through the correlation integral, it propagates to all the coefficients of signal decomposition if they are organized as hierarchical correlations like in the case of wavelets that will be considered in the next section.

5 Concept of the detection and compression scheme for an arbitrary signal

Considerations of the previous sections allows us to propose a signal decomposition scheme that extends ideas of the statistical signal processing and takes into account fundamental limitations of the linear filtration and its statistical properties.

As a starting approach, we chose a time trace decomposition into Daubechies wavelets [11] that are capable to pick up the local spectral properties of the time series by means of the multiscale analysis. This method is able to describe both stationary and transient features of the original time series. The coefficients emerging in this transform are correlation measures between the time series and a particular wavelet placed at a given temporal position and an additive white Gaussian noise component. Because of this the wavelet coefficients are distributed as a Gaussian random variable as it was shown above for the correlation integral. Following this approach, we can use the approach of the statistical signal detection to identify which wavelets correspond to a signal and separate those which rather have noise-only nature. The noise-only wavelets can be rejected as one not holding any interesting information regarding the signal. Within the framework of this approach each wavelet becomes an optimal filter for a particular signal or its part that can be present in more complex astrophysical signals in the time series. Each filter is optimal only to its own part of the entire signal and provides a general framework that allows for decomposing a large class of signals. The payment for such generality is rise of the energy threshold of the signal detection. The reason to expect it comes from the theory of the optimal filtration considered above. Any wavelet is the optimal filter only for a certain wavelet waveform. Thus, a given wavelet uses only part of the energy of the entire signal in contrast to the optimal filter.

Thus, the concept we propose has the following components:

- Autoregressive-moving average filter [12] to whitening the data and decouple the stationary process present in the time series from slow or fast transients.
- Multiscale time trace decomposition using the Daubechies wavelets [11] (the decomposition provides a hierarchical sequence of wavelet coefficients).
- Statistical treatment of each wavelet based on the Neyman–Pearson criterion for identification of noise-only wavelets.
- Estimation of the information content of a given trace following the ideas of the Shannon information theory.

For completeness of the report, the following section reviews the Daubechies wavelet transform and a way to compute it.

5.1 Daubechies wavelets

Daubechies wavelets are a wavelet family that allows for both the decomposition of a signal into wavelets and the reconstruction of the original time series from the wavelet transform [11]. In contrast to other families, these wavelets are rigorously orthogonal. That means that different components of the decomposition are mathematically and physically independent from each other. For completeness of this report, we consider here how the wavelet transform works for this family. The review of the Daubechies wavelets here follow the description in [13].

In general, a discrete wavelet transform is organized as a hierarchical algorithm, as follows:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \\ y_5 \\ y_6 \\ y_7 \\ y_8 \\ y_9 \\ y_{10} \\ y_{11} \\ y_{12} \\ y_{13} \\ y_{14} \\ y_{15} \\ y_{16} \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}
 \xrightarrow{f}
 \begin{array}{c}
 \begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ d_1 \\ s_2 \\ d_2 \\ s_3 \\ d_3 \\ s_4 \\ d_4 \\ s_5 \\ d_5 \\ s_6 \\ d_6 \\ s_7 \\ d_7 \\ s_8 \\ d_8 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}
 \xrightarrow{\text{permute}}
 \begin{array}{c}
 \begin{bmatrix} s_1 \\ s_2 \\ s_3 \\ s_4 \\ s_5 \\ s_6 \\ s_7 \\ s_8 \\ d_1 \\ d_2 \\ d_3 \\ d_4 \\ d_5 \\ d_6 \\ d_7 \\ d_8 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}
 \xrightarrow{f}
 \begin{array}{c}
 \begin{bmatrix} s'_1 \\ d'_1 \\ s'_2 \\ d'_2 \\ s'_3 \\ d'_3 \\ s'_4 \\ d'_4 \\ d_1 \\ d_2 \\ d_3 \\ d_4 \\ d_5 \\ d_6 \\ d_7 \\ d_8 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}
 \xrightarrow{\text{permute}}
 \begin{array}{c}
 \begin{bmatrix} s'_1 \\ s'_2 \\ s'_3 \\ s'_4 \\ d'_1 \\ d'_2 \\ d'_3 \\ d'_4 \\ d_1 \\ d_2 \\ d_3 \\ d_4 \\ d_5 \\ d_6 \\ d_7 \\ d_8 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{array}
 \xrightarrow{f} \dots
 \end{array}
 \tag{44}$$

The vector $\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_{16}]^T$ denotes the original time series consisting of 16 elements in this example. After the transforming this time series with a desired wavelet transform f , we obtain a vector comprised of the “smooth” coefficients s_i and “detailed” coefficients d_i . The theory of wavelet transforms clarifies the nature of this coefficients. Namely, if we treat wavelets as digital filters, they come in pairs of wavelet and corresponding scaling function, separating

6 Definition of information

Several approaches exist that define the concept of information in the context of natural sciences: the combinatorial approach, the probabilistic approach, and the algorithmic approach [17]. The later one is related to the theory of recursive functions and algorithms and does not seem appropriate for the problem we are addressing. The combinatorial and the probabilistic approaches have a clear connection to each other. They were originally developed in the framework of the Shannon information theory [14, 15] that was originally invented to address issues appearing in communication and cryptography.

In the present work, we use the framework of the Shannon information theory. This theory and its tools seem to fit best to the present task of the measurement of the amount of information contained in a measured time series. To identify more clearly the internal meaning of the terminology, the quantities, and the internal meaning of the used approaches, we repeat here the derivation of the most important quantities of the theory. First, we derive the necessary quantities in the combinatorial approach and then extend them to the probabilistic approach. In our derivation we follow the way described in [16].

Let us consider a random variable that may allow for M possible outcomes and each outcome is considered to be equally probable. As a particular example, we can think about a fair dice where $M = 6$. One of the central quantities in information theory is the entropy of a random variable. The entropy should be a function of the number of possible outcomes of the random variable

$$H = f(M). \quad (48)$$

The function $f(\cdot)$ should also be a monotonic function that increases with increase of M . The meaning of entropy in this context is that it measures the amount of uncertainty we have about the outcome. The larger the number of possible outcomes, the larger is the uncertainty regarding to which value to expect in an observation.

We can denote the entropy of the random variable before the observation as the prior entropy H_{pr} , and the entropy after the observation of some particular value of the random variable as the posterior entropy H_{ps} . The amount of information gained by the observation is measured as decrease of entropy (or uncertainty) after the particular value is observed

$$I = H_{\text{pr}} - H_{\text{ps}}. \quad (49)$$

To find the function $f(\cdot)$, we should introduce some principle. Here, we introduce the principle of additivity. Namely, we want to build the entropy in a way such that if a system S is composed of two (independent) sub-systems S_1 and S_2 , the entropy of the large system will be the sum of entropies of the sub-systems. Here is the symbolical expression of this principle

$$H [S = \{S_1, S_2\}] = H [\{S_1\}] + H [\{S_2\}]. \quad (50)$$

For the system of two dice, we have $6^2 = 36$ possible outcomes for the couple of numbers running from 1 to 6 each. By utilizing the principle of additivity, we can write the following equation for this system

$$f(6^2) = f(6) + f(6) = 2f(6). \quad (51)$$

If we generalize this system to n sub-systems each of which has m possible outcomes, we will come to the following expression

$$f(m^n) = nf(m). \quad (52)$$

From this expression we can find the concrete form of the function $f(\cdot)$. To do so, we introduce $x = m^n$ with $n = \ln x / \ln m$, and rewrite equation (52) as

$$f(x) = K \ln x. \quad (53)$$

The constant $K = f(m) / \ln m$ does not hold any useful functional dependence. When we use this function to compute entropy, we arrive at

$$H = K \ln M, \quad (54)$$

also known as Hartley function.

The obtained function $f(\cdot)$ has a property interesting for the measurement of information. In the combinatorial approach, a random variable has M possible outcomes, each of which is equiprobable. When we have observed a value, we have only one outcome $M = 1$ and the entropy in this case reveals $H = K \ln 1 = 0$. This is a desirable property of entropy, as in such a case there is no uncertainty left. Thus, the original information measure (49) becomes identical to the entropy of the original system before observation and we can use the prior entropy alone to measure information.

The constant K appearing in front of the logarithm in the function $f(\cdot)$ specifies the units that we want to use to measure information. Here are three of many possible choices of the units:

$K = 1$	$H_{\text{nat}} = \ln M$	natural units
$K = \frac{1}{\ln 2}$	$H_{\text{bit}} = \frac{1}{\ln 2} \ln M = \log_2 M$	digital units (bit)
$K = k_B$	$H_{\text{ph}} = k_B \ln M$	physical units,

where k_B denotes the Boltzmann constant, which has units energy over temperature. Hereafter we use natural units.

Let us move from the combinatorial approach to the probabilistic approach. If, as before, the random variable ξ may assume any of the M equiprobable values, $(1, \dots, M)$, the probability to observe any of these values is $P(\xi) = 1/M$. By using the Hartley function (54) in natural units and eliminating M , we obtain the value of entropy in terms probability

$$H = -\ln P(\xi). \quad (55)$$

This entropy has a concrete value. If different outcomes are not equiprobable, we use the above expression as a basis for the generalization of concept of entropy. In this case, entropy is a random variable depending on the particular value appearing in the observation

$$H(\xi) = -\ln P(\xi). \quad (56)$$

We can form the expectation (or average) of this random entropy following the standard technique

$$H_{\xi} = \mathbb{E} [H(\xi)] = - \sum_{\xi} P(\xi) \ln P(\xi). \quad (57)$$

This averaged quantity is the Boltzmann or Shannon entropy (here in natural units) and plays an important role in the Shannon information theory.

There are few basic theorems connected to the obtained quantities and results. We list them without proof:

Theorem 1. *Random and average entropy are non-negative.*

Theorem 2. *Entropy attains the maximum value of $\ln M$ when the outcomes (realizations) are equiprobable, i.e. when $P(\xi) = 1/M$.*

Theorem 3. *If two random variables, ξ_1 and ξ_2 , are independent, the total (or joint) entropy $H_{\xi_1\xi_2}$ is the sum of two entropies: $H_{\xi_1\xi_2} = H_{\xi_1} + H_{\xi_2}$.*

7 Discovery potential for test signals

In this section we show examples of estimation of the discovery potential for three test signals. The signals selected here are basic and are not intended to mimic the dispersed astrophysical signal. Selection of the later type of signals, appropriate test parameters for them, and studying features of their detection is the subject for the follow up work.

7.1 Test signals

Gaussian signal. First selected signal is the simple Gaussian waveform

$$s(t) = N \exp\left(-\frac{(t - t_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (58)$$

located at the time interval $t \in [0, 1]$. This waveform is placed in the center of the interval ($t_0 = 0.5$) and is set to have a relatively narrow width, such that most of the energy of the waveform is located within a short time interval ($\sigma = 0.05$). The signal for test is obtained by discretisation of this continuous waveform into 128 samples evenly spaced over the time interval.

Square signal. The square signal is a discrete-time signal with the length of 128 samples. It is defined directly for signal samples. Its first ten values of them are set to a constant value while remaining part of the signal is set to zero

$$s_i = \begin{cases} a, & 0 \leq i < 10. \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (59)$$

The constant a is selected such that the entire signal has a given energy, E .

Square wave signal. The square wave signal is the discrete-time signal continuing the logic of the previous, square signal

$$s_i = \begin{cases} a, & 0 \leq i < 10. \\ -a, & 11 \leq i < 20. \\ a, & 21 \leq i < 30. \\ -a, & 31 \leq i < 40. \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (60)$$

As before, the constant a is set in way that the entire signal has a given energy, E . The total length of the signal is 128 samples.

7.2 Extension of the information measure

For the purposes of this document, we extend the meaning of the probability used in the Hartley function to the probability densities. We follow here a naive logic of extension: substitution of the probabilities with probability densities

$$H = -\ln p(\xi|\xi_0). \quad (61)$$

In this form of extension $p(\xi|\xi_0)$ is the likelihood function for the probability density $p(\xi)$ of the random variable ξ and the observed value of this variable ξ_0 . The probability density corresponding to the noise-only output of the optimal filter has the following simple Gaussian form

$$p(\xi) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{\xi^2}{2\sigma^2}\right). \quad (62)$$

In this case ξ^2 is equal to the energy of the incoming signal E . Since we know this energy, we effectively compute expected amount of information brought by such a signal. By placing this probability density into the Hartley function and making elementary transformations, we come to the convenient formula of the Hartley amount or information or Hartley entropy

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \ln 2\pi + \ln \sigma + \frac{1}{2} \frac{E}{\sigma^2}. \quad (63)$$

This quantity can be treated as amount of information relative to the noise level. As we would expect from the naive understanding of term ‘‘amount of information’’, the larger the signal, the more information it brings into observation. In the other words, the more pronounced signals are more informative for observations.

7.3 Wavelet-based signal detection procedure

Following the general logic of the optimal filter, we created a statistical signal detection procedure in the wavelet domain. First, we obtained the first two moments of the distributions of the wavelet values for the input signal containing only white Gaussian noise with zero mean and unit variance. The length of the noise time series is the same as the length of the signals (128 samples). The resulting moments are depicted on Figure 1 for all available levels. Since the wavelets in the transformation are normalised to have a unit energy, we can see that as expected the wavelet values are centered at zero value and have the same variance as the input noise.

The detection criteria for a signal in the wavelet domain we build in a way that we assume that the signal is detected when any of the wavelet values exceed a preset threshold value. This value we choose to have the desired value of the false signal detection rate for the noise only time series. The only difference from the optimal filter detection above is that the threshold for the wavelet values is applied on their absolute values. The reason for that is simple. The wavelet spectrum for a particular signal can have both positive and negative values of the particular wavelets.

Figure 2 summarizes the resulting discovery potential for the wavelet-based procedure with comparison to the optimal filter. As expected from the theory of the optimal filter, the detection probability depends only on the energy of the signal and its performance is superior.

Figure 1: Statistical distributions of the DB4 wavelet coefficients of different levels.

8 Outlook and further steps

During the reporting period on WP1 the following was done:

1. we identified the deep logical connection between various detection methods within the framework of Bayesian signal detection procedure.
2. we identified a way how to study the impact of the filtration on the discovery potential.
3. we identified a generalized sub-optimal multi-scale signal detection procedure.
4. we identified an information measure that can be used to measure the amount of information relative to noise.

The following further steps are planned:

1. Extend the described detection and compression scheme to wider range of signal classes.
2. Look for other ways of signal transformation that can be used as a generalized way of sub-optimal signal identification and measurement.
3. Develop further the preliminary approach to measure the amount of information in radio telescope streams.

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Figure 2: The discovery potential evaluated for the three discrete-time test signals: Gaussian waveform, square waveform, and square wave waveform. The secondary axis shows the amount of information for the given signals with particular energy. For comparison, the discovery potential for each of the signals was also evaluated with the optimal filtration procedure. For presentation purposes, the value of the false detection rate, F , is set to 10%.

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